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Article

**CHANGES IN BLOOD PRESSURE AFTER SPINAL
ANESTHESIA FOR CAESAREAN SECTION****Dr. Tasmia Tahir¹, Dr. Khadija Tahir¹, Dr. Zeeshan Ahmad¹**¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction and objective: Spinal anesthesia is the popular route of anesthesia in patient for cesarean delivery. The main objective of the study is to find the changes in blood pressure after spinal anesthesia for caesarean section. **Materials and methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during August 2019 to February 2020. The sample size is 100 from the age group 25 to 40. This research was performed while the patient was sitting on the operating table and placing the feet on the stool. Blood pressure, heart rate and oxygen saturation was maintained and electrocardiography was also recorded as vital signs before spinal anesthesia was given. **Results:** Hypotension occurred after the spinal anesthesia in 85% patients and 15% remained with stable blood pressure. Hypotension was considered when systolic blood pressure was less than 90 mm Hg. Postspinal hypotension was treated with injection ephedrine intravenously. Postspinal hypotension was observed in 85% of patients. **Conclusion:** It is concluded from our analysis that spinal anaesthesia is most common technique used for cesarean section. It is a safest and most economical method as compared with general anaesthesia.

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The main objective of the study is to find the changes in blood pressure after spinal anesthesia for caesarean section in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION:

Spinal anesthesia is the popular route of anesthesia in patient for cesarean delivery. Maternal hypotension is a common complication after spinal anesthesia resulting in adverse maternal and fetal outcomes. Prevention and management of post-spinal hypotension (PSH) is continuously investigated [1]. Caesarean section is a common surgical procedure performed for the delivery of the newborn. In caesarean section, spinal anesthesia is mostly used method due to its safety, simplicity and cost effectiveness. During the spinal anesthesia there is a decrease in blood pressure (hypotension) in the patient. Blood pressure defines the force/pressure exerted by the blood on the vessel wall. The quantity of blood pumped by the heart into the aorta is approx 5 L/min in a healthy adult person at rest. The terms which are used to explain arterial blood pressure are systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, pulse pressure and mean arterial pressure [2].

Changes in blood pressure are seen with respect to sex and age. In each heart beat oxygenated blood is pushed into the arteries. In each pulse the systolic blood pressure is 120mm Hg and diastolic blood pressure is about 80mm Hg in an adult person. Pulse pressure is determined by the difference of systolic and diastolic pressure [3].

Spinal hypotension is common in women who receive spinal anaesthesia for Caesarean delivery, with an incidence of up to 71%. Spinal hypotension can occur precipitously and, if severe, can result in important perinatal adverse outcomes, such as maternal nausea and vomiting, fetal acidosis and may be an important contributory factor for maternal death related to regional anaesthesia [4]. Mothers with pre-delivery hypovolaemia may be at risk of cardiovascular collapse because the sympathetic blockade may severely decrease venous return. As a consequence, prevention of spinal hypotension has been a key research area within the field of obstetric anaesthesia [5].

Objectives of the study

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during August 2019 to February 2020. The sample size was 100 from the age group 25 to 40. Blood pressure, heart rate and oxygen saturation were maintained and electrocardiography was also recorded as vital signs before spinal anesthesia was given. Each parturient was given preoperatively, 500 ml haemaccele. A 25-gauge spinal needle was used for anesthesia and introduced at the level of lumbar 3-4 in sub archnoid space in sitting position. The 1.8 ml hyperbaric solution of bupivacaine was injected into the sub archnoid space and 3 liters of oxygen/min with the help of face mask was provided to the patient.

Blood pressure measurement

The blood pressure was noted every 5 minutes until completion of surgery. Ephedrine 5 mg bolus and 10 mg bolus was injected when systolic blood pressure was between 90-100 mm Hg and or when blood pressure was below 90mm Hg, respectively. Nausea/vomiting were also noted during the operation. The readings of blood pressure were noted for 120 minutes at intervals from the start of surgery.

Statistical analysis

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software (version 17). The significant value for $P < .05$ was accepted as statistically significant.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 patients. Hypotension occurred after the spinal anesthesia in 85% patients and 15% remained with stable blood pressure. The percentage distribution of pre-operative, peroperative and postoperative, systolic, diastolic and pulse rate are shown in Table 1. According to the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) status 76.3% parturients were in ASA I and 23.7% Parturients were in ASA II.

Table 1: The normal preoperative, peroperative and postoperative blood pressure and pulse rate of patients.

	Systolic BP range	Patient (%)	Diastolic BP range	Patient (%)	Patient (%) Pulse rate range	Patient (%)
Preoperative	106- 116	11.3	60- 65	1.3	79- 84	30
	117- 127	82.4	66- 71	11.2	85- 90	51.3
	128- 138	5.0	72- 77	28.8	91- 96	11.2
	139- 149	1.3	78- 83	52.5	97- 112	7.5
			84- 89	6.2		
Peroperative	70- 80	36.2	43- 51	1.3	80- 90	12.5
	81- 91	56.3	52- 60	7.5	91- 101	38.7
	92- 102	6.2	61- 69	58.7	102- 112	43.8
	103- 113	1.3	70- 78	32.5	113- 123	5.00
Postoperative	105- 111	2.5	66- 69	5.00	80- 84	7.5
	112- 118	68.7	70- 73	23.7	85- 89	27.4
	119- 125	27.5	74- 77	43.8	90- 94	43.8
	126- 132	1.3	78- 81	27.5	95- 99	21.3

DISCUSSION:

CS is a very common operation performed nearly in every hospital, we assume that dealing with PSH is a daily situation facing anesthetists with variable levels of experience; thus, future research should focus on simple and rapid protocols that can be easily applied by anesthetists with moderate and low experience with minimal need of complex devices or costly drugs [6, 7].

Nausea and vomiting was developed per operatively in spinal anesthesia may be due to anxiety, arterial hypotension, CNS hypo perfusion, and movement of abdominal organs and use of opiates. In this study vasopressin i.e., ephedrine is used for the correction and management of hypotension for C-section after spinal anesthesia. In another research phenylephrine was given and showed no fatal effects on the mother and newborn [8]. The phenylephrine is also a good vasopressin agent. Ephedrine showed no adverse effects on the mother and fetus in hypotensive cases. Ephedrine has effects both on α -adrenergic and β -adrenergic receptors, either directly or indirectly whereas phenylephrine has effect directly on alpha receptors [9].

To prevent spinal hypotension, a number of approaches have been investigated, notably fluid loading, vasopressors, or both. Despite early enthusiasm, the efficacy of fluid loading for preventing spinal hypotension has been called into question. In contrast, the use of vasopressors has gained increasing prominence as the primary technique for the prevention and treatment of spinal hypotension during Caesarean delivery [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded from our analysis that spinal anaesthesia is most common technique used for cesarean section. It is a safest and most economical method as compared with general anaesthesia.

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